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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDU RAZICK** bearing USN **3SU20SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HAKEEM** bearing USN **3SU20SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL JUMAIL** bearing USN **3SU20SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KIDAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL LISSAN M** bearing USN **3SU20SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAHIMAN** bearing USN **3SU20SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHAY NAGARAJ NAIK** bearing USN **3SU20SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK** bearing USN **3SU20SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH C NAIK** bearing USN **3SU20SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH MANIKOTH** bearing USN **3SU20SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMAD SUFAIL A K** bearing USN **3SU20SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED RIFAI T T** bearing USN **3SU20SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHITH. A** bearing USN **3SU20SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMEER AHMAD** bearing USN **3SU20SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARYA B M** bearing USN **3SU20SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHFAQ ASHRAF** bearing USN **3SU20SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASRID IBRAHIM** bearing USN **3SU20SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHUVANESH N** bearing USN **3SU20SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **C K AJITH** bearing USN **3SU20SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEKSHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEKSHITH C S** bearing USN **3SU20SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DENNIS JOHNSON** bearing USN **3SU20SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH** bearing USN **3SU20SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVYA KUMARI H** bearing USN **3SU20SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FALHLURRAHMAN** bearing USN **3SU20SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FOUZAN ABUZAR SOUDAGAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FUWHAD MOHIYUDDIN** bearing USN **3SU20SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GAYATHRI N K** bearing USN **3SU20SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GIRISH KUMAR.C.H** bearing USN **3SU20SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOWRI M MURALI** bearing USN **3SU20SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GURUNANDAN G R** bearing USN **3SU20SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JADEN CEDRIC D SOUZA** bearing USN **3SU20SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JANITH SUJATHAN P.V** bearing USN **3SU20SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JASEEL .C.H** bearing USN **3SU20SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JEEVAN BHANDARY** bearing USN **3SU20SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K ANWESH JAIN** bearing USN **3SU20SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVAN KUMAR S** bearing USN **3SU20SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVYA T** bearing USN **3SU20SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNA RAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAHARI** bearing USN **3SU20SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAKSHITH P C** bearing USN **3SU20SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANDIRA K N** bearing USN **3SU20SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANISH** bearing USN **3SU20SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANVITHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD IJAS.K** bearing USN **3SU20SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AKIF HYDER** bearing USN **3SU20SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARHAN K** bearing USN **3SU20SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SUHAIL** bearing USN **3SU20SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED UBAIS MB** bearing USN **3SU20SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MUHAD** bearing USN **3SU20SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAHIN P K** bearing USN **3SU20SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHIL KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHA R** bearing USN **3SU20SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHITH** bearing USN **3SU20SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUNITH KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU20SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAAD SHAIED AHMED** bearing USN **3SU20SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAGAR H R** bearing USN **3SU20SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDESH H P** bearing USN **3SU20SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJANA NANDAKUMAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYED SHAFQAT SHAFI SAHEB** bearing USN **3SU20SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYYID AFRAS SHIBILI** bearing USN **3SU20SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAMEEM MUHAMMED PUTHIRI** bearing USN **3SU20SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAMITH K POOJARY** bearing USN **3SU20SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHARATH** bearing USN **3SU20SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHEIK MOHAMMED MUSTHAJAB** bearing USN **3SU20SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRADDHA ALVA** bearing USN **3SU20SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRIVITH H V** bearing USN **3SU20SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRUJAN JAYARAM MOOLYA** bearing USN **3SU20SA070** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SINCHANA H C** bearing USN **3SU20SA071** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA S** bearing USN **3SU20SA072** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOORAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA073** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SPOORTHY V D** bearing USN **3SU20SA074** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUMALATHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA075** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHANTH M SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU20SA076** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **T A THANHEEN** bearing USN **3SU20SA077** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **V ADITHYA** bearing USN **3SU20SA078** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIKRAM G RAO** bearing USN **3SU20SA079** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VILAS M KULAL** bearing USN **3SU20SA080** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIRAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA081** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU P** bearing USN **3SU20SA082** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GAURAV RAYKA** bearing USN **3SU20SA083** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **A.M. RUSHAD MUHAMMED** bearing USN **3SU20AI001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITYA RAMCHANDRA PRABHU** bearing USN **3SU20AI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED THAMJEED K A** bearing USN **3SU20AI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALTHAF KHAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **G YADULAL BHASKAR** bearing USN **3SU20AI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GEORGIN SHAJU** bearing USN **3SU20AI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHITHA** bearing USN **3SU20AI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN NAIK S** bearing USN **3SU20AI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SAHEL** bearing USN **3SU20AI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED ZERIN BIN SIRAJ** bearing USN **3SU20AI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMED NIHAL MIRSHA** bearing USN **3SU20AI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SAHAL K K** bearing USN **3SU20AI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NADHEER ABDU NASIR** bearing USN **3SU20AI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAROON JOSEPH** bearing USN **3SU20AI015** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHETTY NIMESH VASU R** bearing USN **3SU20AI016** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREE HARI SUKUMARAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI017** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUBODH. S** bearing USN **3SU20AI018** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINEESH VISWAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI019** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINIL SUMITH MONTEIRO** bearing USN **3SU20AI020** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK V P** bearing USN **3SU20NS001** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANKITH SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU20NS002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **EIJAZ AHMED M P** bearing USN **3SU20NS003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOOSA WAHEED** bearing USN **3SU20NS004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHIK R** bearing USN **3SU20NS005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEJITH PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU20NS006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHAL SHAJI** bearing USN **3SU20NS007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOKUL KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU20NS008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GUDINHO SALDAN CAITAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAZIN MOHAMMED** bearing USN **3SU20CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AQHEEB BASHA G V** bearing USN **3SU20CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAMRAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHMMED RAIYAN ISMAIL KHAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAKHYATH B** bearing USN **3SU20CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDHIN ISSAC ABRAHAM** bearing USN **3SU20CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJEETH SEETHARAMA DEVADIGA** bearing USN **3SU20CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIBLU NUHMAN B** bearing USN **3SU20CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUDARSHANA T** bearing USN **3SU20CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THARUN V** bearing USN **3SU20CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the **I SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YADHUKRISHNAN P** bearing USN **3SU20CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AJMAL KABEER** bearing USN **3SU20CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Analysis of 10 IT Companies** in the I SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2020.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDU RAZICK** bearing USN **3SU20SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HAKEEM** bearing USN **3SU20SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL JUMAIL** bearing USN **3SU20SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KIDAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL LISSAN M** bearing USN **3SU20SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAHIMAN** bearing USN **3SU20SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHAY NAGARAJ NAIK** bearing USN **3SU20SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK** bearing USN **3SU20SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH C NAIK** bearing USN **3SU20SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH MANIKOTH** bearing USN **3SU20SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMAD SUFAIL A K** bearing USN **3SU20SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED RIFAI T T** bearing USN **3SU20SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHITH. A** bearing USN **3SU20SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMEER AHMAD** bearing USN **3SU20SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARYA B M** bearing USN **3SU20SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHFAQ ASHRAF** bearing USN **3SU20SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASRID IBRAHIM** bearing USN **3SU20SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHUVANESH N** bearing USN **3SU20SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **C K AJITH** bearing USN **3SU20SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEKSHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEKSHITH C S** bearing USN **3SU20SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DENNIS JOHNSON** bearing USN **3SU20SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH** bearing USN **3SU20SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVYA KUMARI H** bearing USN **3SU20SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FALHLURRAHMAN** bearing USN **3SU20SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FOUZAN ABUZAR SOUDAGAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FUWHAD MOHIYUDDIN** bearing USN **3SU20SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GAYATHRI N K** bearing USN **3SU20SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GIRISH KUMAR.C.H** bearing USN **3SU20SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOWRI M MURALI** bearing USN **3SU20SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GURUNANDAN G R** bearing USN **3SU20SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JADEN CEDRIC D SOUZA** bearing USN **3SU20SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JANITH SUJATHAN P.V** bearing USN **3SU20SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JASEEL .C.H** bearing USN **3SU20SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JEEVAN BHANDARY** bearing USN **3SU20SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K ANWESH JAIN** bearing USN **3SU20SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVAN KUMAR S** bearing USN **3SU20SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVYA T** bearing USN **3SU20SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNA RAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAHARI** bearing USN **3SU20SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAKSHITH P C** bearing USN **3SU20SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANDIRA K N** bearing USN **3SU20SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANISH** bearing USN **3SU20SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANVITHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD IJAS.K** bearing USN **3SU20SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AKIF HYDER** bearing USN **3SU20SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARHAN K** bearing USN **3SU20SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SUHAIL** bearing USN **3SU20SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED UBAIS MB** bearing USN **3SU20SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MUHAD** bearing USN **3SU20SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAHIN P K** bearing USN **3SU20SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHIL KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHA R** bearing USN **3SU20SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHITH** bearing USN **3SU20SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUNITH KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU20SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAAD SHAIED AHMED** bearing USN **3SU20SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAGAR H R** bearing USN **3SU20SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDESH H P** bearing USN **3SU20SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJANA NANDAKUMAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYED SHAFQAT SHAFI SAHEB** bearing USN **3SU20SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYYID AFRAS SHIBILI** bearing USN **3SU20SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAMEEM MUHAMMED PUTHIRI** bearing USN **3SU20SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAMITH K POOJARY** bearing USN **3SU20SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHARATH** bearing USN **3SU20SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHEIK MOHAMMED MUSTHAJAB** bearing USN **3SU20SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRADDHA ALVA** bearing USN **3SU20SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRIVITH H V** bearing USN **3SU20SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRUJAN JAYARAM MOOLYA** bearing USN **3SU20SA070** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SINCHANA H C** bearing USN **3SU20SA071** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA S** bearing USN **3SU20SA072** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOORAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA073** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SPOORTHY V D** bearing USN **3SU20SA074** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUMALATHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA075** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHANTH M SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU20SA076** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **T A THANHEEN** bearing USN **3SU20SA077** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **V ADITHYA** bearing USN **3SU20SA078** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIKRAM G RAO** bearing USN **3SU20SA079** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VILAS M KULAL** bearing USN **3SU20SA080** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIRAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA081** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU P** bearing USN **3SU20SA082** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GAURAV RAYKA** bearing USN **3SU20SA083** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **A.M. RUSHAID MUHAMMED** bearing USN **3SU20AI001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITYA RAMCHANDRA PRABHU** bearing USN **3SU20AI002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED THAMJEED K A** bearing USN **3SU20AI003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALTHAF KHAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **G YADULAL BHASKAR** bearing USN **3SU20AI005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GEORGIN SHAJU** bearing USN **3SU20AI007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHITHA** bearing USN **3SU20AI008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN NAIK S** bearing USN **3SU20AI009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SAHEL** bearing USN **3SU20AI010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED ZERIN BIN SIRAJ** bearing USN **3SU20AI011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMED NIHAL MIRSHA** bearing USN **3SU20AI012** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SAHAL K K** bearing USN **3SU20AI013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NADHEER ABDU NASIR** bearing USN **3SU20AI014** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAROON JOSEPH** bearing USN **3SU20AI015** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHETTY NIMESH VASU R** bearing USN **3SU20AI016** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREE HARI SUKUMARAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI017** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUBODH. S** bearing USN **3SU20AI018** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINEESH VISWAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI019** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINIL SUMITH MONTEIRO** bearing USN **3SU20AI020** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK V P** bearing USN **3SU20NS001** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANKITH SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU20NS002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **EIJAZ AHMED M P** bearing USN **3SU20NS003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOOSA WAHEED** bearing USN **3SU20NS004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHIK R** bearing USN **3SU20NS005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEJITH PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU20NS006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHAL SHAJI** bearing USN **3SU20NS007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOKUL KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU20NS008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GUDINHO SALDAN CAITAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAZIN MOHAMMED** bearing USN **3SU20CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AQHEEB BASHA G V** bearing USN **3SU20CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAMRAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHMMED RAIYAN ISMAIL KHAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAKHYATH B** bearing USN **3SU20CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDHIN ISSAC ABRAHAM** bearing USN **3SU20CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJEETH SEETHARAMA DEVADIGA** bearing USN **3SU20CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIBLU NUHMAN B** bearing USN **3SU20CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUDARSHANA T** bearing USN **3SU20CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THARUN V** bearing USN **3SU20CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YADHUKRISHNAN P** bearing USN **3SU20CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AJMAL KABEER** bearing USN **3SU20CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **CD Library Management System** in the **II SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2020**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDU RAZICK** bearing USN **3SU20SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HAKEEM** bearing USN **3SU20SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL JUMAIL** bearing USN **3SU20SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KIDAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL LISSAN M** bearing USN **3SU20SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAHIMAN** bearing USN **3SU20SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHAY NAGARAJ NAIK** bearing USN **3SU20SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK** bearing USN **3SU20SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH C NAIK** bearing USN **3SU20SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH MANIKOTH** bearing USN **3SU20SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMAD SUFAIL A K** bearing USN **3SU20SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED RIFAI T T** bearing USN **3SU20SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHITH. A** bearing USN **3SU20SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMEER AHMAD** bearing USN **3SU20SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARYA B M** bearing USN **3SU20SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHFAQ ASHRAF** bearing USN **3SU20SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASRID IBRAHIM** bearing USN **3SU20SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHUVANESH N** bearing USN **3SU20SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **C K AJITH** bearing USN **3SU20SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEKSHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEKSHITH C S** bearing USN **3SU20SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DENNIS JOHNSON** bearing USN **3SU20SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH** bearing USN **3SU20SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVYA KUMARI H** bearing USN **3SU20SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FALHLURRAHMAN** bearing USN **3SU20SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FOUZAN ABUZAR SOUDAGAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FUWHAD MOHIYUDDIN** bearing USN **3SU20SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GAYATHRI N K** bearing USN **3SU20SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GIRISH KUMAR.C.H** bearing USN **3SU20SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOWRI M MURALI** bearing USN **3SU20SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GURUNANDAN G R** bearing USN **3SU20SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JADEN CEDRIC D SOUZA** bearing USN **3SU20SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JANITH SUJATHAN P.V** bearing USN **3SU20SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JASEEL .C.H** bearing USN **3SU20SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JEEVAN BHANDARY** bearing USN **3SU20SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K ANWESH JAIN** bearing USN **3SU20SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVAN KUMAR S** bearing USN **3SU20SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVYA T** bearing USN **3SU20SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNA RAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAHARI** bearing USN **3SU20SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAKSHITH P C** bearing USN **3SU20SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANDIRA K N** bearing USN **3SU20SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANISH** bearing USN **3SU20SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANVITHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD IJAS.K** bearing USN **3SU20SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AKIF HYDER** bearing USN **3SU20SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARHAN K** bearing USN **3SU20SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SUHAIL** bearing USN **3SU20SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED UBAIS MB** bearing USN **3SU20SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MUHAD** bearing USN **3SU20SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAHIN P K** bearing USN **3SU20SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHIL KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHA R** bearing USN **3SU20SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHITH** bearing USN **3SU20SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUNITH KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU20SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAAD SHAIED AHMED** bearing USN **3SU20SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAGAR H R** bearing USN **3SU20SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDESH H P** bearing USN **3SU20SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJANA NANDAKUMAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYED SHAFQAT SHAFI SAHEB** bearing USN **3SU20SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYYID AFRAS SHIBILI** bearing USN **3SU20SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAMEEM MUHAMMED PUTHIRI** bearing USN **3SU20SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAMITH K POOJARY** bearing USN **3SU20SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHARATH** bearing USN **3SU20SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHEIK MOHAMMED MUSTHAJAB** bearing USN **3SU20SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRADDHA ALVA** bearing USN **3SU20SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRIVITH H V** bearing USN **3SU20SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRUJAN JAYARAM MOOLYA** bearing USN **3SU20SA070** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SINCHANA H C** bearing USN **3SU20SA071** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA S** bearing USN **3SU20SA072** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOORAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA073** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SPOORTHY V D** bearing USN **3SU20SA074** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUMALATHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA075** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHANTH M SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU20SA076** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **T A THANHEEN** bearing USN **3SU20SA077** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **V ADITHYA** bearing USN **3SU20SA078** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIKRAM G RAO** bearing USN **3SU20SA079** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VILAS M KULAL** bearing USN **3SU20SA080** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIRAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA081** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU P** bearing USN **3SU20SA082** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GAURAV RAYKA** bearing USN **3SU20SA083** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **A.M. RUSHAD MUHAMMED** bearing USN **3SU20AI001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITYA RAMCHANDRA PRABHU** bearing USN **3SU20AI002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED THAMJEED K A** bearing USN **3SU20AI003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALTHAF KHAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **G YADULAL BHASKAR** bearing USN **3SU20AI005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GEORGIN SHAJU** bearing USN **3SU20AI007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHITHA** bearing USN **3SU20AI008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN NAIK S** bearing USN **3SU20AI009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SAHEL** bearing USN **3SU20AI010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED ZERIN BIN SIRAJ** bearing USN **3SU20AI011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMED NIHAL MIRSHA** bearing USN **3SU20AI012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SAHAL K K** bearing USN **3SU20AI013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NADHEER ABDU NASIR** bearing USN **3SU20AI014** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAROON JOSEPH** bearing USN **3SU20AI015** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHETTY NIMESH VASU R** bearing USN **3SU20AI016** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREE HARI SUKUMARAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI017** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUBODH. S** bearing USN **3SU20AI018** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINEESH VISWAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI019** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINIL SUMITH MONTEIRO** bearing USN **3SU20AI020** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK V P** bearing USN **3SU20NS001** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANKITH SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU20NS002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **EIJAZ AHMED M P** bearing USN **3SU20NS003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOOSA WAHEED** bearing USN **3SU20NS004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHIK R** bearing USN **3SU20NS005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEJITH PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU20NS006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHAL SHAJI** bearing USN **3SU20NS007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOKUL KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU20NS008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GUDINHO SALDAN CAITAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAZIN MOHAMMED** bearing USN **3SU20CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AQHEEB BASHA G V** bearing USN **3SU20CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAMRAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHMMED RAIYAN ISMAIL KHAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAKHYATH B** bearing USN **3SU20CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDHIN ISSAC ABRAHAM** bearing USN **3SU20CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJEETH SEETHARAMA DEVADIGA** bearing USN **3SU20CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIBLU NUHMAN B** bearing USN **3SU20CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUDARSHANA T** bearing USN **3SU20CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THARUN V** bearing USN **3SU20CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YADHUKRISHNAN P** bearing USN **3SU20CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AJMAL KABEER** bearing USN **3SU20CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **College management system** in the **III SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDU RAZICK** bearing USN **3SU20SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HAKEEM** bearing USN **3SU20SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL JUMAIL** bearing USN **3SU20SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KIDAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL LISSAN M** bearing USN **3SU20SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAHIMAN** bearing USN **3SU20SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHAY NAGARAJ NAIK** bearing USN **3SU20SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK** bearing USN **3SU20SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH C NAIK** bearing USN **3SU20SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH MANIKOTH** bearing USN **3SU20SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMAD SUFAIL A K** bearing USN **3SU20SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED RIFAI T T** bearing USN **3SU20SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHITH. A** bearing USN **3SU20SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMEER AHMAD** bearing USN **3SU20SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARYA B M** bearing USN **3SU20SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHFAQ ASHRAF** bearing USN **3SU20SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASRID IBRAHIM** bearing USN **3SU20SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHUVANESH N** bearing USN **3SU20SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **C K AJITH** bearing USN **3SU20SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEKSHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEKSHITH C S** bearing USN **3SU20SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DENNIS JOHNSON** bearing USN **3SU20SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH** bearing USN **3SU20SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVYA KUMARI H** bearing USN **3SU20SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FALHLURRAHMAN** bearing USN **3SU20SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FOUZAN ABUZAR SOUDAGAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FUWHAD MOHIYUDDIN** bearing USN **3SU20SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GAYATHRI N K** bearing USN **3SU20SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GIRISH KUMAR.C.H** bearing USN **3SU20SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOWRI M MURALI** bearing USN **3SU20SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GURUNANDAN G R** bearing USN **3SU20SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JADEN CEDRIC D SOUZA** bearing USN **3SU20SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JANITH SUJATHAN P.V** bearing USN **3SU20SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JASEEL .C.H** bearing USN **3SU20SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JEEVAN BHANDARY** bearing USN **3SU20SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K ANWESH JAIN** bearing USN **3SU20SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVAN KUMAR S** bearing USN **3SU20SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVYA T** bearing USN **3SU20SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNA RAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAHARI** bearing USN **3SU20SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAKSHITH P C** bearing USN **3SU20SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANDIRA K N** bearing USN **3SU20SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANISH** bearing USN **3SU20SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANVITHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD IJAS.K** bearing USN **3SU20SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AKIF HYDER** bearing USN **3SU20SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARHAN K** bearing USN **3SU20SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SUHAIL** bearing USN **3SU20SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED UBAIS MB** bearing USN **3SU20SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MUHAD** bearing USN **3SU20SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAHIN P K** bearing USN **3SU20SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHIL KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHA R** bearing USN **3SU20SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHITH** bearing USN **3SU20SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUNITH KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU20SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAAD SHAIED AHMED** bearing USN **3SU20SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAGAR H R** bearing USN **3SU20SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDESH H P** bearing USN **3SU20SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJANA NANDAKUMAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYED SHAFQAT SHAFI SAHEB** bearing USN **3SU20SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYYID AFRAS SHIBILI** bearing USN **3SU20SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAMEEM MUHAMMED PUTHIRI** bearing USN **3SU20SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAMITH K POOJARY** bearing USN **3SU20SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHARATH** bearing USN **3SU20SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHEIK MOHAMMED MUSTHAJAB** bearing USN **3SU20SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRADDHA ALVA** bearing USN **3SU20SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRIVITH H V** bearing USN **3SU20SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRUJAN JAYARAM MOOLYA** bearing USN **3SU20SA070** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SINCHANA H C** bearing USN **3SU20SA071** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA S** bearing USN **3SU20SA072** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOORAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA073** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SPOORTHY V D** bearing USN **3SU20SA074** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUMALATHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA075** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHANTH M SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU20SA076** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **T A THANHEEN** bearing USN **3SU20SA077** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **V ADITHYA** bearing USN **3SU20SA078** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIKRAM G RAO** bearing USN **3SU20SA079** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VILAS M KULAL** bearing USN **3SU20SA080** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIRAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA081** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the IV SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2021.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU P** bearing USN **3SU20SA082** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GAURAV RAYKA** bearing USN **3SU20SA083** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **A.M. RUSHAD MUHAMMED** bearing USN **3SU20AI001** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITYA RAMCHANDRA PRABHU** bearing USN **3SU20AI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED THAMJEED K A** bearing USN **3SU20AI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALTHAF KHAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **G YADULAL BHASKAR** bearing USN **3SU20AI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GEORGIN SHAJU** bearing USN **3SU20AI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHITHA** bearing USN **3SU20AI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN NAIK S** bearing USN **3SU20AI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SAHEL** bearing USN **3SU20AI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED ZERIN BIN SIRAJ** bearing USN **3SU20AI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMED NIHAL MIRSHA** bearing USN **3SU20AI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SAHAL K K** bearing USN **3SU20AI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NADHEER ABDU NASIR** bearing USN **3SU20AI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAROON JOSEPH** bearing USN **3SU20AI015** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHETTY NIMESH VASU R** bearing USN **3SU20AI016** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREE HARI SUKUMARAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI017** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUBODH. S** bearing USN **3SU20AI018** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINEESH VISWAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI019** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINIL SUMITH MONTEIRO** bearing USN **3SU20AI020** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK V P** bearing USN **3SU20NS001** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANKITH SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU20NS002** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **EIJAZ AHMED M P** bearing USN **3SU20NS003** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOOSA WAHEED** bearing USN **3SU20NS004** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHIK R** bearing USN **3SU20NS005** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEJITH PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU20NS006** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHAL SHAJI** bearing USN **3SU20NS007** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOKUL KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU20NS008** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GUDINHO SALDAN CAITAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAZIN MOHAMMED** bearing USN **3SU20CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AQHEEB BASHA G V** bearing USN **3SU20CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAMRAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHMMED RAIYAN ISMAIL KHAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAKHYATH B** bearing USN **3SU20CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDHIN ISSAC ABRAHAM** bearing USN **3SU20CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJEETH SEETHARAMA DEVADIGA** bearing USN **3SU20CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIBLU NUHMAN B** bearing USN **3SU20CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUDARSHANA T** bearing USN **3SU20CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THARUN V** bearing USN **3SU20CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YADHUKRISHNAN P** bearing USN **3SU20CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AJMAL KABEER** bearing USN **3SU20CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Document Management System** in the **IV SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2021**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDU RAZICK** bearing USN **3SU20SA001** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL HAKEEM** bearing USN **3SU20SA002** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL JUMAIL** bearing USN **3SU20SA003** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL KIDAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA004** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL LISSAN M** bearing USN **3SU20SA005** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABDUL RAHIMAN** bearing USN **3SU20SA006** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHAY NAGARAJ NAIK** bearing USN **3SU20SA007** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK** bearing USN **3SU20SA008** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH C NAIK** bearing USN **3SU20SA009** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADARSH MANIKOTH** bearing USN **3SU20SA010** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMAD SUFAIL A K** bearing USN **3SU20SA011** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED RIFAI T T** bearing USN **3SU20SA012** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AKSHITH. A** bearing USN **3SU20SA013** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AMEER AHMAD** bearing USN **3SU20SA014** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ARYA B M** bearing USN **3SU20SA015** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASHFAQ ASHRAF** bearing USN **3SU20SA016** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ASRID IBRAHIM** bearing USN **3SU20SA017** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **BHUVANESH N** bearing USN **3SU20SA018** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **C K AJITH** bearing USN **3SU20SA019** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEKSHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA020** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DEEKSHITH C S** bearing USN **3SU20SA021** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DENNIS JOHNSON** bearing USN **3SU20SA022** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DHANUSH** bearing USN **3SU20SA023** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **DIVYA KUMARI H** bearing USN **3SU20SA024** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FALHLURRAHMAN** bearing USN **3SU20SA025** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FOUZAN ABUZAR SOUDAGAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA026** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **FUWHAD MOHIYUDDIN** bearing USN **3SU20SA027** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GAYATHRI N K** bearing USN **3SU20SA028** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GIRISH KUMAR.C.H** bearing USN **3SU20SA029** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOWRI M MURALI** bearing USN **3SU20SA030** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GURUNANDAN G R** bearing USN **3SU20SA031** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JADEN CEDRIC D SOUZA** bearing USN **3SU20SA032** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JANITH SUJATHAN P.V** bearing USN **3SU20SA033** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JASEEL .C.H** bearing USN **3SU20SA034** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **JEEVAN BHANDARY** bearing USN **3SU20SA035** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **K ANWESH JAIN** bearing USN **3SU20SA036** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVAN KUMAR S** bearing USN **3SU20SA037** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KAVYA T** bearing USN **3SU20SA038** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KRISHNA RAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA039** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAHARI** bearing USN **3SU20SA040** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **LAKSHITH P C** bearing USN **3SU20SA041** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANDIRA K N** bearing USN **3SU20SA042** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANISH** bearing USN **3SU20SA043** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MANVITHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA044** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMAD IJAS.K** bearing USN **3SU20SA045** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AKIF HYDER** bearing USN **3SU20SA046** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAHAMMED ANAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA047** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARAS** bearing USN **3SU20SA048** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED FARHAN K** bearing USN **3SU20SA049** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SUHAIL** bearing USN **3SU20SA050** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED UBAIS MB** bearing USN **3SU20SA051** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED MUHAD** bearing USN **3SU20SA052** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SHAHIN P K** bearing USN **3SU20SA053** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NIKHIL KUMAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA054** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHA R** bearing USN **3SU20SA055** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NISHITH** bearing USN **3SU20SA056** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PUNITH KUMAR M** bearing USN **3SU20SA057** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAAD SHAIED AHMED** bearing USN **3SU20SA058** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAGAR H R** bearing USN **3SU20SA059** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANDESH H P** bearing USN **3SU20SA060** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJANA NANDAKUMAR** bearing USN **3SU20SA061** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYED SHAFQAT SHAFI SAHEB** bearing USN **3SU20SA062** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SAYYID AFRAS SHIBILI** bearing USN **3SU20SA063** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAMEEM MUHAMMED PUTHIRI** bearing USN **3SU20SA064** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAMITH K POOJARY** bearing USN **3SU20SA065** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHARATH** bearing USN **3SU20SA066** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHEIK MOHAMMED MUSTHAJAB** bearing USN **3SU20SA067** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRADDHA ALVA** bearing USN **3SU20SA068** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRIVITH H V** bearing USN **3SU20SA069** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHRUJAN JAYARAM MOOLYA** bearing USN **3SU20SA070** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SINCHANA H C** bearing USN **3SU20SA071** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SNEHA S** bearing USN **3SU20SA072** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SOORAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA073** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SPOORTHY V D** bearing USN **3SU20SA074** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUMALATHA** bearing USN **3SU20SA075** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUSHANTH M SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU20SA076** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **T A THANHEEN** bearing USN **3SU20SA077** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **V ADITHYA** bearing USN **3SU20SA078** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIKRAM G RAO** bearing USN **3SU20SA079** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VILAS M KULAL** bearing USN **3SU20SA080** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VIRAJ** bearing USN **3SU20SA081** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHNU P** bearing USN **3SU20SA082** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GAURAV RAYKA** bearing USN **3SU20SA083** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **A.M. RUSHAD MUHAMMED** bearing USN **3SU20AI001** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ADITYA RAMCHANDRA PRABHU** bearing USN **3SU20AI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **AHAMMED THAMJEED K A** bearing USN **3SU20AI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ALTHAF KHAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **G YADULAL BHASKAR** bearing USN **3SU20AI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GEORGIN SHAJU** bearing USN **3SU20AI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **HARSHITHA** bearing USN **3SU20AI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **KIRAN NAIK S** bearing USN **3SU20AI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED SAHEL** bearing USN **3SU20AI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMED ZERIN BIN SIRAJ** bearing USN **3SU20AI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMED NIHAL MIRSHA** bearing USN **3SU20AI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MUHAMMED SAHAL K K** bearing USN **3SU20AI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **NADHEER ABDU NASIR** bearing USN **3SU20AI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHAROON JOSEPH** bearing USN **3SU20AI015** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHETTY NIMESH VASU R** bearing USN **3SU20AI016** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREE HARI SUKUMARAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI017** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUBODH. S** bearing USN **3SU20AI018** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINEESH VISWAN** bearing USN **3SU20AI019** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VINIL SUMITH MONTEIRO** bearing USN **3SU20AI020** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ABHISHEK V P** bearing USN **3SU20NS001** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **ANKITH SHETTY** bearing USN **3SU20NS002** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **EIJAZ AHMED M P** bearing USN **3SU20NS003** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOOSA WAHEED** bearing USN **3SU20NS004** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRATHIK R** bearing USN **3SU20NS005** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SREEJITH PRASAD** bearing USN **3SU20NS006** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **VISHAL SHAJI** bearing USN **3SU20NS007** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GOKUL KRISHNAN** bearing USN **3SU20NS008** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **GUDINHO SALDAN CAITAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI002** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MAZIN MOHAMMED** bearing USN **3SU20CI003** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AQHEEB BASHA G V** bearing USN **3SU20CI004** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED SHAMRAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI005** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHMMED RAIYAN ISMAIL KHAN** bearing USN **3SU20CI006** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **PRAKHYATH B** bearing USN **3SU20CI007** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **RIDHIN ISSAC ABRAHAM** bearing USN **3SU20CI008** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the V SEM of the BCA programme for the academic year 2022.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SANJEETH SEETHARAMA DEVADIGA** bearing USN **3SU20CI009** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the BCA programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SHIBLU NUHMAN B** bearing USN **3SU20CI010** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **SUDARSHANA T** bearing USN **3SU20CI011** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **THARUN V** bearing USN **3SU20CI012** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms **YADHUKRISHNAN P** bearing USN **3SU20CI013** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms **MOHAMMED AJMAL KABEER** bearing USN **3SU20CI014** has completed his/her minor project on **Hospital Management System** in the **V SEM** of the **BCA** programme for the academic year **2022**.

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